

Practicing care-full scholarship in research, education, & collaboration: An analytical framework

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Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing call in the scientific community to critically re-think and re-orient our practices towards a care-full model of scholarship. This call is particularly urgent in pockets of academia which are keen to explore new paradigms and ways of working in the many contexts of practice researchers engage in, be it research-driven participatory work (e.g. Moriggi et al. 2020a; Sellberg et al. 2021), education (e.g. Tassone et al. 2017; Deanna and Ryan 2021), and/or inter- and trans-disciplinary collaborations (e.g. Corbera et al. 2020; OCare et al. 2021).

The changes imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic have accelerated the call for more responsible and sustainable forms of scholarship that account for both societal and researchers' needs. The pandemic has indeed exacerbated and made visible some of the maladies and contradictions characterizing the current systems of knowledge production. An example of these maladies is the elitist, compartmentalized, and extractive nature of established ways of producing knowledge, which fail to be attentive to real-world needs and challenges and to have a meaningful impact of societies (Fazey et al. 2020). At the same time, the neo-liberal trend characterizing academic institutions, and the related growing demands for performance and productivity to advance one's own career, result in unsustainable burdens on scholars' shoulders, who often feel exhausted, alienated, and torn by conflicting emotions and life experiences (Sellberg et al. 2021; Corbera et al. 2020).

Fischer and Tronto defined care as: 'A species activity that includes everything we do to maintain, continue and repair our "world" so that we can live in it as well as possible. That world includes our bodies, ourselves and our environment, all of which we seek to interweave in a complex, life-sustaining web' (Tronto, 2013, 19). As engaged scholars, our "world" includes also academia, and the multifold relations we perform within and outside of it, which shape our identities and experiences profoundly.

Against this background, I claim that, in order to transform the current system towards a care-full model of academia – attentive to both societal, students, and researchers' needs – we need to give stronger attention to *what* scholars do, *why*, and *how*. This is important to enhance our capacity for reflexivity and critical thinking, but also to recognize and appreciate the care-full modes of working that are already practiced and performed by many researchers across different fields and areas of engagement. To do so, I draw from feminist relational thinking, long used to uncover dismissed perspectives and bring them to the fore (Gibson-Graham 2006; Pulcini 2013). A relational approach highlights the web of connections and processes that enmesh people and their surroundings (Tschakert & St. Clair 2013). From a relational perspective, knowledge is neither static nor the exclusive prerogative of some particular groups; rather, knowledge is 'in becoming', shaped and co-created by all sides engaged (Moriggi et al. 2020a).

Inspired by care ethics literature and relational and feminist theories, this working paper proposes an analytical framework to critically reflect upon different ways of being and practicing care-full scholarship, which is briefly presented in the following section.

An analytical framework for a reflexive care-full practice

This working paper aims at shedding light on two dimensions of change (Lonsdale et al. 2015) that have been so far overlooked with regards to scholarship (Sellberg et al. 2021; OCare et al. 2021):

- 1) care-full scholars' *personal and inner dimension*: i.e. the values, needs, motivations, and concerns that drive their work;
- 2) care-full scholars' *relational engagements*: the tangible practices they perform when engaging with research participants, students, and colleagues.

To make these two dimensions visible, I propose an analytical framework to support scholars' reflexivity regarding their practices in three contexts of engagement and of knowledge co-production: a) research-driven participatory work; b) teaching and education; c) inter-and trans-disciplinary collaborations (oriented towards community building and net-weaving).

The framework is informed by the ethics of care literature and in particular by the five stages of caring identified by Tronto (2013) and later adapted by Moriggi et al. (2020b). As illustrated by Figure 1, Tronto's model is innovative for two main reasons: a) it shows that caring is an iterative cycle, and not a one-time intervention, and can thus be a dynamic, adaptive, and possibly transformative process; b) it highlights the dual nature of caring, expressed by means of ethical principles *and* through embodied practices (Tronto 2013).

Figure 1. Five stages of caring and related moral principles (inspired by Tronto 2013, and adapted from Moriggi et al. 2020b)

The analytical framework proposed in this working paper is composed of a set of analytical questions, meant as reflexivity prompts for scholars who identify themselves as care-full and who wish to critically reflect upon the care-fullness of their practices. Earlier operationalization of Tronto’s five stages of caring can be found in Moriggi et al. (2020b), where the authors investigate the caring practices in three cases of nature-based social entrepreneurship. The moral principles outlined by Tronto also served as “moral compass” to guide and reflect upon the participatory engagement in my PhD study (Moriggi 2021, p.36).

The analytical questions of the framework are summarized in Table 1, and are briefly explained below. In real life, the five stages of caring do not necessarily happen in a linear, consecutive way. Moreover, all the stages are interconnected and can overlap throughout the process. For the sake of analytical clarity, they are presented here in a systematic way, starting from ‘caring about’ and ending with ‘caring with’.

Dimension of the caring process	Moral principle	Empirical Question(s)
CARING ABOUT	Attentiveness	What needs are care-full scholars attentive to? And what concerns, motivations and drives inform their practices?
CARING FOR	Response-ability	How are care-full scholars able to respond to what they are/have become attentive to? What practices do they perform, in order to translate those needs, concerns, and motivations into a tangible course/event/process?
CARE GIVING	Competence	How are practices of research, teaching, and collaboration implemented in care-full ways? What specific ways of working and underlying principles do care-full scholars embody through their practices? And what constraints and challenges do they encounter in the process?
CARE RECEIVING	Responsiveness	How do care-full scholars create opportunities for those they engage with to be active and responsive throughout the process? Which mechanisms for feed-back and feed-forward are created and which ones are not and why?
CARING WITH	Reciprocity	In which ways is the care-full process oriented towards mutual learning, co-becoming and transformation of all sides involved?

Table 1. An ethics of care-inspired analytical framework to reflect upon care-full scholarship (Version 1.0)

According to Tronto, the process of caring starts with ‘caring about’, the moment in which we become attentive to needs around us. The first question in the framework is ‘*What needs are care-full scholars attentive to?*’ This question refers to both scholars’ own personal needs and to the needs of those they engage in their practices – be it participants in their research, students they teach to, or colleagues they collaborate with. To shed light on scholars’ identity and positionality, it is also important to ask ‘*What concerns, motivations, and drives inform the practice of care-full scholars?*’, giving voice to what individuals care about at various levels – personal, organizational, and societal ones.

When attention becomes intention, we enter the stage of ‘caring for’. As a result of a practice of relationality, scholars become response-able, i.e. able to respond to the needs they have identified earlier. The question here is ‘*How are care-full scholars able to respond to what they are/have become attentive to? What practices do they perform, in order to translate those needs, concerns, and motivations into a tangible course/event/process?*’ When answering this question, it is important to reflect upon both ‘visible’ and ‘invisible’ practices of care, focusing on the multitude of everyday tasks we take on, not all of which are recognized and appreciated in the current system.

The stage of 'care giving' delves deeper into the actual practice of caring. The question here is *'How are practices of research, teaching, and collaboration implemented in care-full ways? What specific ways of working and underlying principles do care-full scholars embody through their practices? And what constraints and challenges do they encounter in the process?'* Doing things in care-full ways requires specific skills and attitudes, which Tronto (2013) summarizes with 'competence', referring not only to technical and scientific knowledge, but also to a certain moral disposition, which allows us to do things in purposeful and meaningful ways.

'Care receiving' is the fourth stage in the caring process, which makes visible how caring is not a unilateral doing, but rather a reciprocal dynamic process, that involves more than one side. According to Tronto, the "other side" of the caring spectrum should be given the chance to respond to the care given, commenting on its quality and effectiveness. Possible identified gaps or unmet needs can trigger the start of a new caring cycle (Tronto 2013). The question here is *'How do care-full scholars create opportunities for those they engage to be active and responsive throughout the process? Which mechanisms for feed-back and feed-forward are created and which ones are not and why?'*

The model outlined by Tronto ends with 'caring with', which is a stage encompassing all the other ones. It stems from the idea that the entire process of caring should be carried out in a way that recognizes everyone's dignity and knowledge, and that creates the necessary conditions for empowerment. Tronto sees this stage as aligning with the principle of 'solidarity'. Based on a review of the ethics of care literature, I prefer to use the term 'reciprocity', to highlight the possibility for mutual learning, co-becoming, and change that may be triggered through care-full practices (Moriggi et al. 2020b). With regards to the field of scholarship, the question here is *'In which ways is the care-full process oriented towards mutual learning, co-becoming, and transformation of all sides involved?'*

Concluding thoughts & future steps

The proposed framework is the first step of a co-creative process aimed at producing a joint publication on care-full scholarship. The process involves a working group of several co-authors from different academic institutions. The analytical questions proposed in version 1.0 of the framework are the result of an iterative learning process, which is currently ongoing and will continue in the coming months. Further iterations of the framework will benefit from reflections of all contributors to the paper, based on their hands-on experience practicing care-full scholarship in different contexts of engagement. This process will ideally lead to an empirically-grounded heuristic that can inspire other scholars to reflect upon their care-full practices in research, teaching, and collaboration.

The paper will engage critically with questions of care in academia, to avoid the risk of idealizing or trivializing the term, and to understand what care-fullness means and how it is practiced. Additionally, the hope of the working group is to contribute to developing stronger awareness regarding the factors constraining or hindering care-full practice, such as the institutional or organizational environment in which certain scholars operate. Moreover, the paper will also deal with questions of self-care, shedding light on the delicate balance between caring and *carrying*, and between the joys and burdens of caring.

Acknowledgements

I wish to express my gratitude to Anke de Vrieze (Wageningen University), Valentina Tassone (Wageningen University), Meghann Ormond (Wageningen University), and Daniele Brombal (Ca' Foscari University of Venice), for the precious reflections they shared in various occasions, which contributed to shape this working paper to its current version. I am also grateful to all the colleagues who participated in the Transformative Learning Hub session on 'care and transformative learning' and to those who took part in the first 'Gathering on care-full scholarship', whose thoughts and enthusiasm have been crucial to initiate our working group on care-full scholarship.

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